

Surface Family with a Common Natural Geodesic Lift

Evren Ergün

Ondokuz Mayıs University

Çarşamba Chamber of Commerce Vocational School, Çarşamba, Samsun, Turkey

Ergin Bayram

Ondokuz Mayıs University

Faculty of Arts and Sciences, Department of Mathematics, Samsun, Turkey

E-mail: eergun@omu.edu.tr, erginbayram@yahoo.com

Abstract: In the present paper, we find a surface family possessing the natural lift of a given curve as a geodesic. We express necessary and sufficient conditions for the given curve such that its natural lift is a geodesic on any member of the surface family. We present a sufficient condition for ruled surfaces with the above property. Finally, we illustrate the method with some examples.

Key Words: Ruled surfaces, curve, geodesic, Frenet frame.

AMS(2010): 53A04, 53A05.

§1. Introduction

Curves and surfaces play an important role in differential geometry. In recent years, there is an ascending interest on finding surfaces possessing a given curve as a common curve instead of finding and characterizing curves on a given surface. In 2004, Wang et. al. [1] proposed a method to find surfaces having a given curve as a common geodesic. Kasap et. al. [2] generalized the marching-scale functions of Wang and obtained a larger family of surfaces. Li et. al. [3] derived the necessary and sufficient constraint for a line of curvature. Bayram et. al. [4] studied parametric surfaces which interpolate a given curve as a common asymptotic. Ergün et. al. [5] obtained a surface family from a given spacelike or timelike line of curvature in Minkowski 3-space.

Inspired with the above studies, we find a surface family possessing the natural lift of a given curve as a common geodesic. We obtain the sufficient condition for the resulting surface to be a ruled surface.

We start with presenting some background. A parametric curve $\alpha(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, is a curve on a surface $P(s,t)$ in \mathbb{R}^3 that has a constant s or t -parameter value. In this paper, α' denotes the derivative of α with respect to arc length parameter s and we assume that α is a regular curve with $\alpha''(s) \neq 0$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$. For every point of $\alpha(s)$, the set

¹Received May 12, 2015, Accepted February 8, 2016.

$\{T(s), N(s), B(s)\}$ is called the Frenet frame along $\alpha(s)$, where $T(s) = \frac{\alpha'(s)}{\|\alpha'(s)\|}$, $N(s) = \frac{\alpha''(s) - \langle \alpha''(s), T(s) \rangle T(s)}{\|\alpha''(s) - \langle \alpha''(s), T(s) \rangle T(s)\|}$ and $B(s) = T(s) \times N(s)$ are the unit tangent, principal normal, and binormal vectors of the curve at the point $\alpha(s)$, respectively. Derivative formulas of the Frenet frame is governed by the relations

$$\frac{d}{ds} \begin{pmatrix} T(s) \\ N(s) \\ B(s) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \kappa(s) & 0 \\ -\kappa(s) & 0 & \tau(s) \\ 0 & -\tau(s) & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} T(s) \\ N(s) \\ B(s) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\kappa(s) = \|\alpha''(s)\|$ and $\tau(s) = -\langle B'(s), N(s) \rangle$ are called the curvature and torsion of the curve $\alpha(s)$, respectively [6].

Let M be a surface in \mathbb{R}^3 and let $\alpha : I \rightarrow M$ be a parameterized curve. α is called an integral curve of X if

$$\frac{d}{ds}(\alpha(s)) = X(\alpha(s)) \quad (\text{for all } t \in I),$$

where X is a smooth tangent vector field on M . We have

$$TM = \bigcup_{P \in M} T_P M = \chi(M),$$

where $T_P M$ is the tangent space of M at P and $\chi(M)$ is the space of tangent vector fields on M .

For any parameterized curve $\alpha : I \rightarrow M$, $\bar{\alpha} : I \rightarrow TM$ given by ([7])

$$\bar{\alpha}(s) = (\alpha(s), \alpha'(s)) = \alpha'(s)|_{\alpha(s)} \quad (2)$$

is called the *natural lift* of α on TM .

If a rigid body moves along a unit speed curve $\alpha(s)$, then the motion of the body consists of translation along α and rotation about α . The rotation is determined by an angular velocity vector ω which satisfies $T' = \omega \times T$, $N' = \omega \times N$ and $B' = \omega \times B$. The vector ω is called the *Darboux vector*. In terms of Frenet vectors T , N and B , Darboux vector is given by $\omega = \tau T + \kappa B$ [8]. Also, we have $\kappa = \|\omega\| \cos \theta$, $\tau = \|\omega\| \sin \theta$, where θ is the angle between the Darboux vector ω and binormal vector $B(s)$ of α . Observe that $\theta = \arctan \frac{\tau}{\kappa}$ (Fig. 1).

Fig.1 Darboux vector ω , tangent vector T and binormal vector B of α

Let $\alpha(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, be an arc length curve and $\bar{\alpha}(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, be the natural

lift of α . Then we have

$$\begin{pmatrix} \bar{T}(s) \\ \bar{N}(s) \\ \bar{B}(s) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\cos \theta & 0 & \sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} T(s) \\ N(s) \\ B(s) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where $\{T(s), N(s), B(s)\}$ and $\{\bar{T}(s), \bar{N}(s), \bar{B}(s)\}$ are the Frenet frames of the curves α and $\bar{\alpha}$, respectively, and θ is the angle between the Darboux vector and binormal vector of α .

§2. Surface Family with a Common Natural Geodesic Lift

Suppose we are given a 3-dimensional parametric curve $\alpha(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, in which s is the arc length and $\|\alpha''(s)\| \neq 0$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$. Let $\bar{\alpha}(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, be the involute of $\alpha(s)$.

Surface family that interpolates $\bar{\alpha}(s)$ as a common curve is given in the parametric form as

$$P(s, t) = \bar{\alpha}(s) + u(s, t)\bar{T}(s) + v(s, t)\bar{N}(s) + w(s, t)\bar{B}(s), \quad (4)$$

$L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, $T_1 \leq t \leq T_2$, where $u(s, t)$, $v(s, t)$ and $w(s, t)$ are C^1 functions and are called *marching-scale functions* and $\{\bar{T}(s), \bar{N}(s), \bar{B}(s)\}$ is the Frenet frame of the curve $\bar{\alpha}$. Using Eqn. (3) we can express Eqn. (4) in terms of Frenet frame $\{T(s), N(s), B(s)\}$ of the curve α as

$$\begin{aligned} P(s, t) &= \bar{\alpha}(s) + (w(s, t)\sin \theta - v(s, t)\cos \theta)T(s) \\ &\quad + u(s, t)N(s) + (v(s, t)\sin \theta + w(s, t)\cos \theta)B(s), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, $T_1 \leq t \leq T_2$.

Remark 1 Observe that choosing different marching-scale functions yields different surfaces possessing $\bar{\alpha}(s)$ as a common curve.

Our goal is to find the necessary and sufficient conditions for which the curve $\bar{\alpha}(s)$ is isoparametric and geodesic on the surface $P(s, t)$. Firstly, as $\bar{\alpha}(s)$ is an isoparametric curve on the surface $P(s, t)$, there exists a parameter $t_0 \in [T_1, T_2]$ such that

$$u(s, t_0) = v(s, t_0) = w(s, t_0) \equiv 0, \quad L_1 \leq s \leq L_2, \quad T_1 \leq t_0 \leq T_2. \quad (6)$$

Secondly the curve $\bar{\alpha}$ is geodesic on the surface $P(s, t)$ if and only if along the curve the surface normal vector field $n(s, t_0)$ is parallel to the principal normal vector field \bar{N} of the curve $\bar{\alpha}$. The normal vector of $P(s, t)$ can be written as

$$n(s, t) = \frac{\partial P(s, t)}{\partial s} \times \frac{\partial P(s, t)}{\partial t}.$$

By Eqns. (3) and (5), the normal vector along the curve $\bar{\alpha}$ can be expressed as

$$n(s, t_0) = \kappa \left[-\frac{\partial w}{\partial t}(s, t_0) \bar{N}(s) + \frac{\partial v}{\partial t}(s, t_0) \bar{B}(s) \right], \quad (7)$$

where κ is the curvature of the curve α . Since $\kappa(s) \neq 0$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, the curve $\bar{\alpha}$ is a geodesic on the surface $P(s, t)$ if and only if

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t}(s, t_0) \neq 0, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial t}(s, t_0) \equiv 0.$$

So, we can present:

Theorem 2 *Let $\alpha(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, be a unit speed curve with nonvanishing curvature and $\bar{\alpha}(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, be its natural lift. $\bar{\alpha}(s)$ is a geodesic on the surface (4) if and only if*

$$\begin{cases} u(s, t_0) = v(s, t_0) = w(s, t_0) \equiv 0, \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial t}(s, t_0) \neq 0, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial t}(s, t_0) \equiv 0, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, $T_1 \leq t$, $t_0 \leq T_2$ (t_0 fixed).

Corollary 3 *Let $\alpha(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, be a unit speed curve with nonvanishing curvature and $\bar{\alpha}(s)$, $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, be its natural lift. If*

$$u(s, t) = w(s, t) = (t - t_0), \quad v(s, t) \equiv 0, \quad (9)$$

where $L_1 \leq s \leq L_2$, $T_1 \leq t, t_0 \leq T_2$ (t_0 fixed) then (4) is a ruled surface and $\bar{\alpha}$ is a geodesic on it.

§3. Examples

Example 1 Let $\alpha(s) = \left(\frac{4}{5} \cos s, 1 - \sin s, -\frac{3}{5} \cos s\right)$ be a unit speed curve. Then, it is easy to show that

$$\begin{aligned} T(s) &= \left(-\frac{4}{5} \sin s, -\cos s, \frac{3}{5} \sin s\right), \\ N(s) &= \left(-\frac{4}{5} \cos s, \sin s, \frac{3}{5} \cos s\right), \\ B(s) &= \left(-\frac{3}{5}, 0, -\frac{4}{5}\right), \\ \kappa &= 1, \quad \tau = 0, \quad \theta = 0. \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\bar{\alpha}(s) = \left(-\frac{4}{5} \sin s, -\cos s, \frac{3}{5} \sin s\right)$$

as the natural lift of α with Frenet vectors

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{T}(s) &= \left(-\frac{4}{5} \cos s, \sin s, \frac{3}{5} \cos s \right), \\ \bar{N}(s) &= \left(\frac{4}{5} \sin s, \cos s, -\frac{3}{5} \sin s \right), \\ \bar{B}(s) &= \left(-\frac{3}{5}, 0, -\frac{4}{5} \right).\end{aligned}$$

If we choose $u(s, t) = w(s, t) = t$, $v(s, t) \equiv 0$, then Eqn. (9) is satisfied and we get the ruled surface

$$\begin{aligned}P_1(s, t) &= \bar{\alpha}(s) + t [\bar{T}(s) + \bar{B}(s)] \\ &= \left(-\frac{4}{5} (\sin s + t \cos s) - \frac{3}{5} t, t \sin s - \cos s, \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{3}{5} (\sin s + t \cos s) - \frac{4}{5} t \right),\end{aligned}$$

$-2 < s \leq 2$, $-1 \leq t \leq 1$, possessing $\bar{\alpha}$ as a geodesic such as those shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2 Ruled surface $P_1(s; t)$ as a member of the surface family and its common natural geodesic lift $\bar{\alpha}$

For the same curve, if we choose $u(s, t) = e^{2t} - 1$, $v(s, t) \equiv 0$, $w(s, t) = t$, then Eqn. (8) is satisfied and we obtain the surface

$$\begin{aligned}P_2(s, t) &= \bar{\alpha}(s) + (e^{2t} - 1) \bar{T}(s) + t \bar{B}(s) \\ &= \left(-\frac{4}{5} ((e^{2t} - 1) \cos s + \sin s) - \frac{3}{5} t, (e^{2t} - 1) \sin s - \cos s, \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{3}{5} ((e^{2t} - 1) \cos s + \sin s) - \frac{4}{5} t \right),\end{aligned}$$

where $-3 < s \leq 3$, $-1 \leq t \leq 1$ interpolating $\bar{\alpha}$ as the natural geodesic lift (Fig. 3).

Fig.3 $P_2(s;t)$ as a member of the surface family and its common natural geodesic lift $\bar{\alpha}$

Example 2 Let $\alpha(s) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sin s, \frac{s}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos s\right)$ be an arc length helix. One can show that

$$\begin{aligned} T(s) &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos s, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sin s\right), \\ N(s) &= (-\sin s, 0, -\cos s), \\ B(s) &= \left(-\frac{1}{2} \cos s, \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \sin s\right), \\ \kappa &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, \quad \tau = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \theta = \frac{\pi}{6}. \end{aligned}$$

We obtain

$$\bar{\alpha}(s) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos s, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sin s\right)$$

as the natural lift of α with Frenet vectors

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}(s) &= (-\sin s, 0, -\cos s), \\ \bar{N}(s) &= (-\cos s, 0, \sin s), \\ \bar{B}(s) &= (0, 1, 0). \end{aligned}$$

Choosing marching scale functions as $u(s,t) = s^2t$, $v(s,t) \equiv 0$, $w(s,t) = \sin t$ we get the

surface

$$\begin{aligned} P_3(s, t) &= \bar{\alpha}(s) + s^2 t \bar{T}(s) + \sin t \bar{B}(s) \\ &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos s - s^2 t \sin s, \frac{1}{2} + \sin t, -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sin s - s^2 t \cos s \right) \end{aligned}$$

satisfying Eqn. (8) possessing $\bar{\alpha}$ as a common natural geodesic lift (Fig. 4).

Fig.4 $P_3(s, t)$ as a member of the surface family and its common natural geodesic lift $\bar{\alpha}$

If we let $u(s, t) = s \tan t$, $v(s, t) = (\cos t) - 1$, $w(s, t) = s \sin t$, then Eqn. (8) is satisfied and we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_4(s, t) &= \bar{\alpha}(s) + s \tan t \bar{T}(s) + (\cos t - 1) \bar{N}(s) + s \sin t \bar{B}(s) \\ &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos s - s (\tan t) \sin s + \cos s (1 - \cos t), \frac{1}{2} + s \sin t, \right. \\ &\quad \left. -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sin s - s (\tan t) \cos s + \sin s (\cos t - 1) \right), \end{aligned}$$

$0 < s \leq 3$, $0 \leq t \leq 1$, as a member of the surface family possessing $\bar{\alpha}$ as a common natural geodesic lift shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5 $P_4(s, t)$ as a member of the surface family and its common natural geodesic lift $\bar{\alpha}$.

Acknowledgments

The second author would like to thank TUBITAK (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey) for their financial supports during his doctorate studies.

References

- [1] G.J.Wang, K.Tang and C.L.Tai, Parametric representation of a surface pencil with a common spatial geodesic, *Comput. Aided Des.*, 36 (5) (2004), 447-459.
- [2] E.Kasap, F.T. Akyıldız and K.Orbay, A generalization of surfaces family with common spatial geodesic. *Appl. Math. Comput*
- [3] C.Y. Li, R.H. Wang and C.G.Zhu, Parametric representation of a surface pencil with a common line of curvature. *Comput. Aided Des.*, 43 (9) (2011), 1110–1117.
- [4] E.Bayram, F.Güler and E.Kasap, Parametric representation of a surface pencil with a common asymptotic curve. *Comput. Aided Des.*, 44 (2012), 637-643.
- [5] E.Ergün, E.Bayram and E.Kasap, Surface pencil with a common line of curvature in Minkowski 3-space. *Acta Math. Sinica, English Series*. 30 (12) (2014), 2103-2118.
- [6] M.P. do Carmo, *Differential geometry of curves and surfaces*, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey 1976.
- [7] J.A. Thorpe, *Elementary topics in differential geometry*, Springer-Verlag, New York 1979.
- [8] J. Oprea, *Differential geometry and its applications* , Pearson Education Inc., USA 2006.